

MODELING EUROPA RIDING THE BULL: A KNOWLEDGE GRAPH ON CIC. NAT. DEO. AND THE SCULPTURE BY N. KOUNDOUROS

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INTRODUCTION

This is the first version of my work for the MA course on Digital Classics.

Aim

Model the myth of Europa through a Knowledge Graph Editor (KGE), linking its literary articulation in *De Natura Deorum* 1.78 with its visual representation in the sculpture *The Abduction of Europa* by N. Koundouros located in Agios Nikolaos, Crete.

- Why does Cicero mention the myth of Europa?
- Why did Koundouros envision the abduction of Europa this way?

METHODS

Through the Knowledge Graph Editor, I connect:

- *DE NATURA DEORUM*.
- *THE ABDUCTION OF EUROPA*.

I have used:

- KGE (Knowledge Graph Editor).
- Wikidata (For Europa, Cicero, *De Natura Deorum*).
- Wikipedia- FOR THE MYTH OF EUROPA.
- Loeb Library for a **close reading analysis** of the text. Secondary, scholar bibliography will be used.of the text.

**CONNECTING PAST WITH MODERN ART.
CONSTRUCTING STRUCTURED, INTERCONNECTED DATA.**

RESULTS

**THE ABDUCTION OF EUROPA
(2012, AGIOS NICHOLAOS, CRETE).**

REFERENCES

FOR *THE ABDUCTION OF EUROPA* AND *DE NATURA DEORUM*, VISIT RESPECTIVELY:

TALOS Project, *KNOWLEDGE GRAPH EDITOR* (V1.5):

<http://talos-ai4ssh.eu/kge/v15/>

FOR CICERO, *DE DANTURA DEORUM*, EUROPA:

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

FOR THE MYTH OF EUROPA:

<https://scaife.perseus.org/reader/urn:cts:greekLit:tlg0035.tlg02.perseus-grc2:1-166>

https://www.loebclassics.com/view/marcus_tullius_cicero-de-natura_deorum/1933/pb_LCL268.75.xml

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

Future work:

- **Location** of people, where each artifact was created/is located?
- Depictions of individuals riding monsters. Look at *De. Nat. Deo.*: **Triton**.
- How can gods be depicted or visualized?